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Summary

This deliverable 2.5 summarises TCforBE Work Package 2 which maps, characterises and assesses consumer country transformative governance innovations for biodiversity and equity. It brings together insights from Deliverables 1 to 4 which sought to understand and explore the role of consumption governance in food systems. The report brings together insights on international trade, legal innovations, consumer behaviour, and collective action to identify pathways for shifting food systems toward sustainability. The purpose is to identify potential change pathways that could guide more sustainable and equitable cocoa and coffee supply chains. In this context, a pathway refers to a sequence of actions or developments that can drive meaningful change. The closely related concept of a leverage point (commonly used in systems thinking) highlights strategic places in a system where interventions can have significant effects. Leverage points, defined as “places within a complex system (such as an economy, a corporation, a city, or an ecosystem) where a small shift in one thing can produce big changes in everything” are framed to present priority points for system intervention, and also represent the point of power. The report synthesizes how systems can be changed through such leverage points and how they together can form different pathways. While leverage points framing is useful, it has also been subject to critique of being too simplifying and mechanical. Therefore, in this work, we primarily use the term *pathways*, while acknowledging that some literature refers to *leverage points*, which we perceive as components of pathways. We do not apply these terms rigidly, as excessive precision could constrain creativity in the development of pathways. Importantly, *pathways* and *leverage points* are not regarded as competing or mutually exclusive concepts.

Rather than introducing additional theory or external sources, we synthesise deliverables: WP2.2 on trade, corporate governance and legal strategies transformative change pathways for biodiversity and equity based on (Santika et al., 2024, Santika et al., 2025) on international trade agreements and (Banwell et al., 2025) on legal actions, WP2.3 on consumer markets (Ingenbleek et al. under review); and deliverable 2.4 on Social movements and collective action in processes of sustainability transformations. We also include an abstract of a forthcoming paper by Benitez-Kanter et al. (2025) on the consumption-driven leverage points which could foster a transformative change of telecoupled value chains towards biodiversity and equity. This integration provides a coherent basis for identifying and outlining change pathways that can reduce the biodiversity, and equity impacts of telecoupled value chains of agrifood commodities entering Europe and the United Kingdom.

International trade analysis shows that while environmental clauses in trade agreements and voluntary certification schemes have expanded, their impacts on biodiversity and social outcomes remain limited and uneven. Certification tends to produce mixed environmental and social benefits; trade agreements often shift environmental impacts from wealthy to poorer nations. Stronger measures—such as producer-led certification systems, rigorous footprint accounting, ecological premiums, and reduced consumption of forest-risk commodities—are identified as essential. More transformative proposals include debt cancellation, structural economic reforms, and challenging global patterns of accumulation.

Legal pathways range from reformist instruments, such as Environmental Due Diligence (e.g., EUDR), to more transformative approaches: Rights of Nature, legal personhood, Ecocide, Restorative Justice, and Environmental Courts. While due diligence embodies incremental change, deeper reforms seek to challenge anthropocentric legal systems and provide mechanisms to hold powerful actors accountable. The combined use of Rights of Nature, Ecocide, and Restorative Justice—supported by specialized tribunals and societal learning—is seen to offer greater transformative potential by reshaping human–nature relations and empowering Indigenous and local communities.

Consumer-behaviour research highlights that consumers desire change but feel constrained within supermarket-dominated environments. Price interventions are the most preferred mechanism, especially lowering prices of sustainable products and increasing those of unsustainable ones. Consumers also favour strengthened sustainability labels, in-store rankings, loyalty rewards, and clearer cues that simplify sustainable choices. They value freedom of choice and resist bans, preferring structural changes in retail environments over individual responsibility. This suggests pathways centred on reshaping retail spaces, improving sustainability information, creating feedback loops, and enabling government action to influence retailer practices.

Collective action findings show that sustainable transitions require deeper socio-political shifts, including new imaginaries of human–nature relations, recognition of more-than-human agency, social learning, and attention to structural barriers shaped by coloniality, gender, and power. Case studies demonstrate that local knowledge and empowerment are critical but often constrained by broader systems. Effective transformation must integrate community-driven approaches and plural knowledge systems.

A **cross-WP synthesis** identifies areas of convergence—such as the need for transparency, accountability, price signals, and strengthened sustainability frameworks—though divergent perspectives remain regarding the depth of change needed. Incremental approaches (certification, pricing, consumer nudges) coexist with calls for radical structural transformation (ontological shifts, decolonial reforms, reducing consumption, reconfigured trade and legal regimes). The emerging conceptual frameworks emphasize systems thinking, combining shallow and deep leverage points, decentralizing governance, and coordinating stakeholders across levels.

Overall, Deliverable 2.5 concludes that transformative change for biodiversity and equity requires combining incremental adjustments with deep systemic shifts. Bridging international trade reforms, legal innovations, consumer-side interventions, and collective action is essential for reshaping telecoupled food systems and aligning EU and UK consumption with sustainable and equitable global outcomes.

1. Introduction

The dual crises of climate change and biodiversity loss are intricately linked to how we produce, distribute, and consume food. Agriculture and food production are significant contributors to greenhouse gas emissions, accounting for approximately a third of global anthropogenic GHG emissions (Crippa et al., 2021). In addition, the expansion of agricultural land and the intensification of farming practices have led to significant biodiversity loss (Cabernard et al., 2024; Pereira et al., 2025). As such, the global food system is at a critical juncture, facing unprecedented challenges that necessitate transformative change in economic, social and financial models (IPBES, 2024) to address biodiversity and equity outcomes. Transformative change refers to **“a fundamental, system-wide reorganisation across technological, economic, and social factors, including paradigms, goals, and values. This reorganisation is necessary for the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity, ensuring a good quality of life and sustainable development”** . (IPBES, 2024, p. 9). In our globalised market environment, food systems can be seen as telecoupled food systems (Hermans et al., 2023), closely linked through market dynamics. The consumption side of food systems and its governance therefore present crucial pathways for transformative change due to its direct and indirect influences on production practices, market dynamics, environmental impacts, and social equity.

Consumer choices, world views, beliefs and values drive actors' behaviour in value chains, which in turn ripples through the value chain, shaping agricultural practices and food production methods. Moreover, consumer awareness and demand for sustainably produced food can incentivize producers to adopt environmentally friendly practices, such as regenerative agriculture, organic farming, or innovative technology-driven farming practices. This can create positive feedback loops, where sustainable consumption patterns support sustainable production methods, ultimately leading to a more resilient and equitable food system. In return, consumers choices are also shaped by market dynamics and the role of people as both consumers and citizens (Bevir & Trentmann, 2007).

The need to look at how consumption is governed in transformative change work arises from the recognition that shifting food systems toward sustainability requires more than just changes in production; it demands a rethinking of how consumption is shaped, regulated, and influenced by a wide array of actors and institutions. However, solely considering 'consumption' would be insufficient, as it lacks understanding of the wider institutional setting and systems of power. Therefore, we refer to consumption governance as it includes the systems of power, institutional arrangements, stakeholders and policy frameworks that shape and are shaped by individual and collective consumption practices across the entire value chain (Eakin et al., 2017; Garrett et al., 2021; Ingram et al., 2020). It recognises that consumers influence production decisions through their preferences and behaviours, but also that these choices are themselves influenced by broader actors such as governments, corporations, NGOs, and media, having the potential to innovate the existing food systems.

The telecoupling (i.e. human and natural systems in different, distant places become connected and influence each other) of food systems and consumption governance are especially apparent in key commodity value chains (Hermans et al., 2023). For example, cocoa and coffee are widely consumed in the EU and UK, but their production often comes at a cost to biodiversity and social equity in the countries where they are grown. Addressing these impacts requires rethinking the role that consumption in the EU and UK plays in shaping global production systems. Within the TforBE project, Work Package 2 (WP2) is dedicated to answering a central question: what can be done in the EU and UK to reduce these negative effects?

This report, Deliverable 2.5, builds on the earlier work of WP2 by bringing together the insights from Deliverables 1–4. The purpose is to identify potential change pathways that could guide more sustainable and equitable cocoa and coffee supply chains. In this context, a pathway refers to a sequence of actions or developments that can drive meaningful change. The closely related concept of a leverage point (commonly used in systems thinking) highlights strategic places in a system where interventions can have significant effects. Leverage points were coined by Meadows (1999) as a tool for thinking about transitions in a system thinking scholarship (Abson et al., 2017;

Chan et al., 2020; Leventon et al., 2021; D. Meadows, 1999). They framed leverage points as “places within a complex system (such as an economy, a corporation, a city, or an ecosystem) where a small shift in one thing can produce big changes in everything” (Meadows, 1999, p. 1) As leverage points are framed to present priority points for system intervention, they also represent the point of power (Chan et al., 2020; D. H. Meadows, 1999). The main interest is in understanding how systems can be changed through such leverage points and how they together can form different pathways. While leverage points framing is useful, it has also been subject to critique of being too simplifying and mechanical. Therefore, in this work, we primarily use the term *pathways*, while acknowledging that some literature refers to *leverage points*, which we perceive as components of pathways. We do not apply these terms rigidly, as excessive precision could constrain creativity in the development of pathways. Importantly, *pathways* and *leverage points* are not regarded as competing or mutually exclusive concepts.

Summarising the work in WP2, this report aims to understand and explore the role of consumption governance in food systems. Rather than introducing additional theory or external sources, we concentrate on synthesising the contributions of WP2's previous deliverables: WP2.2 Analysis of trade, corporate governance and legal strategies transformative change pathways for biodiversity and equity based on (Santika et al., 2024, Santika et al., 2025) on international trade agreements and (Banwell et al., 2025) on legal actions, and WP2.3 on consumer markets (Ingenbleek et al. under review). This integration provides a coherent basis for identifying and outlining change pathways that can reduce the biodiversity and equity impacts of cocoa and coffee consumption in the EU and UK.

2. International Trade

As part of WP2.1 trade and corporate governance strategies were analysed to inform the development of transformative change pathways for biodiversity and equity.

The *Leverage points for tackling unsustainable global value chains: market-based measures versus transformative alternatives* paper by Santika et al. (2024) conducted a comprehensive analysis of existing data on global trade and consumption patterns of tropical commodities, attribution of commodity production to deforestation, trade agreements, and progress in the implementation of crop sustainability standards. Global data on the trade in the tropical commodities of oil palm, cocoa, and coffee were used for this analysis. The analysis focuses on the environmental clauses in trade agreements and sustainability standards -certification schemes and other leverage points that could be part of pathways, such as reducing consumption and more transformative approaches .

The paper starts out analysing market based leverage points , however, as the authors suggest there is limited impact for transformative change, additional more radical leverage points are proposed towards changing consumption patterns and the broader structures of capitalist accumulation. This advocates for giving local people a central role as decision-makers in conservation planning and focusing on behavioural change to create greater democracy in the current telecoupled power structures.

2.2 Environmental clauses in trade agreements

The paper notes that environmental provision has generally been lacking in trade policies, but pressing concerns about deforestation have led to increasing inclusion of environmental elements in regional and bilateral trade agreements. Evidence from the WTO RTA database shows that 195 out of 512 trade agreements signed between 1980 and 2022 contain environmental clauses. These clauses are classified by strength (very weak, weak, medium, strong). Very weak agreements contain only a brief reference to the environment or sustainable development. Weak agreements have more text on commitment but lack details on reviewing processes. Medium agreements include a more substantial review of the impact on sustainability and the role of public participation. Strong agreements include a set of environmental criteria for defining the sustainability of traded goods.

Pressing concerns about deforestation risk embodied in tropical commodity imports have led some high-income country (HIC) governments, including the EU and UK, to propose new legislation mandating supply chain due diligence for forest-risk commodity imports, which marks the beginning of a formal legislative process aimed at reducing deforestation associated with trade. The inclusion of environmental clauses has become more common over time. After 2000-2009, 'weak' agreements became the most common category, and 'medium' and 'strong' agreements increased from 9.5% in 2010-2019 to 28.9% in the last few years. The majority of 'medium' or 'strong' agreements between 2000 and 2022 featured the EU and/or the UK as a part of the 195 trade agreements reviewed that contained environmental clauses, only two were classified as "strong". These strong agreements showcase the most robust internal pathways, specifically by incorporating a clause dedicated to biodiversity that explicitly recognizes the need to respect and preserve traditional knowledge and the practices of indigenous communities. To address equity, they establish review mechanisms, involving both government and civil society, to assess the trade impacts concerning environmental, labour, and human rights issues. These agreements also include detailed environmental commitments, procedures for consultations, cooperative measures to strengthen government sustainability standards, and a commitment not to fail to enforce environmental laws in ways that affect trade or investment.

The paper suggests that meeting certain environmental criteria could be linked to reductions in import duties. WTO regulations require such criteria to be based on performance rather than descriptive characteristics, meaning trade preference for 'sustainable oil palm' is permissible, but specifying it as only RSPO-certified products would not be. HICs would need to define criteria for each forest-risk commodity that any supplier could meet. However, the paper cautions that trade agreements are not intrinsically well-suited to pursuing socio-environmental outcomes as they primarily focus on removing trade restrictions rather than incentivizing different modes of production or consumption, which is the aim of environmental policy .

However, the authors argue that market-based initiatives, including environmental clauses in trade deals, are fundamentally inadequate to tackle socio-ecological degradation given the inherent expansionary nature of global market dynamics. Transformative pathways are required to address the root causes of the problem, such as power inequalities and concentrations of wealth. These transformative approaches call for moderating market fundamentalism, privatization, accumulation, and extraction, while amplifying solidarity and ethics of care. Transformative change centered on equity also requires radical policy prescriptions beyond trade regulation, including debt cancellation for poorer nations that were colonized, taxing agro-commodity companies to internalize their environmental impacts, increasing accountability of corporate impacts, and ensuring local people have a central role as decision-makers in planning

2.3 Sustainability standards – certification schemes

The paper provides an analysis of the evidence regarding the effectiveness and impact of sustainability standards and certification schemes, particularly for oil palm, cocoa, and coffee. The impact of certification varied across different dimensions and commodities. Studies on oil palm covered both plantations and independent smallholders, while studies on cocoa and coffee focused on independent smallholders and medium-scale farms. The environmental impact of certification for oil palm (deforestation and biodiversity, GHG emission, and water and soil management) was neutral or negligible. The social impact (poverty, human rights, and land tenure) tended to be negative. Studies on human rights, land tenure, and GHG emissions were more common for oil palm, likely reflecting the prevalence of large-scale plantations and peatland cultivation. The impact of certification tended to be positive for cocoa on the environmental sustainability indicators. The impact on poverty and income appeared positive. Similar to cocoa, the impact of certification tended to be positive on the environmental sustainability indicators for coffee. Certification impact on poverty and income appeared mixed (positive and neutral).

Sustainability standards, such as voluntary certification schemes, are generally categorized as reform-oriented market-based initiatives, and the paper argues they are ultimately inadequate to achieve transformative change for biodiversity and equity given the inherent expansionary nature of global market dynamics. Evidence of their effectiveness is mixed; for instance, certifications for oil palm often show neutral or negligible environmental benefits (like for deforestation and biodiversity) but can have negative social impacts regarding poverty, income, human rights, and

land tenure. Transformative pathways require moving beyond simply using standards in isolation, as current voluntary standards face hurdles such as high costs and time burdens for smallholders, lack of comprehensive coverage, and the perception by low/middle-income countries that they are Western-dominated systems imposed without considering local development priorities. If environmental criteria are to be effectively incorporated (a deeper reform path), trade restrictions must be coupled with a process of reform of environmental policy and land governance in the producer country, supported by a reward system for sustainably produced products and capacity-building assistance from donor countries. Furthermore, the paper discusses the potential of supporting improvements in producer countries' own certification systems as a more effective approach.

2.3 Other leverage points: Reducing consumption, monitoring crop footprints and decoupling

Based on the limitations of environmental clauses in trade agreements and sustainability standards and certification schemes, additional leverage points for tackling unsustainable global value chains within the food system, particularly in relation to deforestation associated with tropical commodities are suggested in the paper. These leverage points range from reform-oriented, market-based measures to more transformative alternatives,

Reducing Consumption of tropical commodities: The paper highlights that high-income countries (HICs) have the highest per capita consumption of forest-risk commodities like oil palm, cocoa, and coffee, and these consumption rates have dramatically increased. The authors suggest that HICs have the largest responsibility and capability to reduce their consumption. Potential strategies include Applying consumption taxes on forest-risk commodities and their derivatives, whether domestically produced or imported. Revenue from these taxes could be recycled to support smallholder farmers and environmental programs in producing countries. Implementing import duties on forest-risk commodities, with the generated revenue used to support sustainable agriculture and environmental monitoring in producing countries. However, the paper notes that existing trade agreements might limit the ability of some HICs to increase import duties. Facilitating more ambitious transformative shifts in the food system and dietary behaviour towards more locally adapted food consumption patterns and minimizing food waste in HICs and urban areas of emerging economies. Utilizing public procurement as a tool to incentivize more sustainable production. Supporting movements seeking to territorialise food and agricultural production, such as small-scale agriculture, agroecology, and reduced use of transgenic crops, possibly through grant funding and land reform.

Enhancing monitoring of crop environmental footprints: Improved monitoring through detailed spatiotemporal data is identified as a crucial leverage point. The study found that approaches using rudimentary data on crop distribution tend to underestimate deforestation risk. Detailed spatiotemporal change in land cover derived from satellite images can offer more accurate monitoring of both large-scale plantations and smallholder farms. This enhanced monitoring, coupled with trade data, can inform environmental policy measures. However, the paper warns that this focus on information should not distract from addressing the fundamental features of capitalist relations.

Alternatives: Uncoupling, consumption and behaviour change, locally designed approaches, debt cancellation: Recognizing the limitations of market-based mechanisms, the paper explores more radical, transformative approaches. It emphasizes the need to address the power inequalities and concentrations of wealth within agrifood systems. Uncoupling global value chains is suggested as a way to lessen social and environmental costs, although some trade will still be necessary. This includes exploring local production and potential for substitutions. The paper calls for a shift in focus from production zones to the root causes of the problem, including consumption patterns and the broader structures of capitalist accumulation. It advocates for giving local people a central role as decision-makers in conservation planning and focusing on behavioural change to create greater democracy in larger power structures. Radical options such as debt cancellation for poorer nations, taxing agro-commodity companies, increased regulation, support for locally designed approaches to strengthen autonomy, commoning and post-growth approaches to lead to some uncoupling of trade and territorialising of economic activity to fit within planetary boundaries and allow for plural values.

The *Trade agreements and environmental provisions: a counterfactual analysis of environmental impact shifting under global economic inequality* paper by Santika et al (2025) discusses that regional trade agreements (RTAs) have proliferated in recent decades, with increasingly stringent environmental clauses aimed at mitigating trade impacts. However, studies on the environmental effects of RTAs typically focus on a few agreements and indicators, hindering a comprehensive understanding of their effects across various resources. Additionally, the long-term effectiveness of environmental provisions within RTAs remains unclear. To address this gap, the authors applied a rigorous counterfactual analysis to evaluate changes in multiple resource footprints associated with RTAs and environmental provisions across 195 countries annually from 1990 to 2018. They examined four key resources: primary energy, raw materials, blue water, and land use.

Findings revealed that RTAs were linked to the outsourcing of environmental footprints across all resource types while reducing footprint insourcing, a phenomenon known as environmental impact shifting. This effect was particularly evident in wealthier countries, where outsourcing of primary energy, primarily from lower-income nations, rose by 11.6%, raw materials by 13.6%, and land use by 33.5%, compared to similar non-RTA countries. Furthermore, these countries' insourcing of primary energy was reduced by 48.3% and blue water by 15.4% relative to non-RTA counterparts. This is new evidence that outsourcing of environmental impacts is intensifying, with increasing RTAs driving higher resource transfers in recent decades. While stricter environmental provisions in RTAs have been introduced as a short-term measure, they have proven neither sufficient nor sustainable. The growing demands of affluent nations further challenge the long-term effectiveness of such measures. Environmental provisions within RTAs had limited long-term effectiveness in reducing environmental footprints outsourcing. Global trends show a growing disparity in resource use between wealthy and poor countries, exacerbated by RTAs. Rigorous footprint accounting and a resource-equity mechanism, including ecological premiums for resource-intensive imports, are essential within RTAs.

The evidence presented in this article reinforces other sources that demonstrate the stark inequalities in international trade, involving significant flows of resource from poorer to wealthier nations and the outsourcing of negative environmental impacts. Concurrently, poorer nations, which serve as the primary suppliers of global resources, are increasingly burdened by climate change, exacerbating their vulnerability to the cycle of resource exploitation and socio-ecological harm. Broader evidence indicates that environmental degradation and climate change pose increasing barriers to economic growth, while there is insufficient evidence supporting the feasibility of green growth decoupling at the scale, speed, and permanence required.

2.4 Footprint accountability, degrowth, structural trade reforms, and policies addressing overconsumption

The findings underscore the urgent need for deliberate policies that to tackle overconsumption, rising inequality, and ecological harm. Affluent nations need to reduce their material consumption to mitigate the socio-ecological impacts of resource extraction in less affluent countries. Engaging in open dialogue about imposing absolute limits on consumption, guided by the principles of material sufficiency, may offer a constructive path forward. They reiterate [Dunlop and Volker \(2023\)](#), that achieving sustainability requires a clearer understanding of what defines “needs” and “enough” in the context of consumption, enabling us to reshape material supply and consumption systems accordingly. Achieving meaningful sustainability transformations demands not only the adoption of degrowth strategies but also comprehensive structural reforms to the global financial architecture. In parallel, integrating environmental footprint data into assessments of a country's environmental performance is essential for mitigating biases that disproportionately benefit high-consumption nations that rely on outsourcing production. As such data becomes more accessible, these metrics can better align national environmental performance with the UN SDGs, particularly Goal 12 (responsible consumption and production). Reforming RTAs to incorporate ecological footprint accountability and establish resource-equity mechanisms, such as ecological premiums on resource-intensive imports, represents a critical step toward sustainable global practices. Finally, whilst our analysis shows that RTAs and current environmental measures often have negative or limited effects, this should not be seen as an argument for isolationism or protectionism. Instead, we advocate for critically rethinking trade frameworks through the lens of ecological limits and

distributive justice, ensuring that economic integration supports, rather than undermines, environmental sustainability and global equity.

The authors conclude that wealthier, importing nations must adopt more accountable consumption-based governance, prioritising reductions in material consumption to alleviate the socio-ecological impacts on poorer countries.

3. Legal Actions

As part of WP2.1 legal strategies were analysed to inform the development of transformative change pathways for biodiversity and equity.

The *Achieving sustainability transformations for multi-species justice: assessing the potential of diverse legal pathways and societal struggles* paper by Banwell et al (2025) explores the transformative potential of legal pathways and societal struggles to conserve biodiversity and achieve sustainability transformations toward multi-species justice. They explore a range of potential pathways, some that build on existing biodiversity and environmental instruments and supply chain mechanisms, such as Environmental due diligence, to newly emerging, more radical propositions like Rights of Nature and legal personhood, legal recognition for ecocide, restorative Justice, and environmental courts and tribunals. The authors reviews existing literature and empirical cases to examine and reflect on their transformative potential, and to identify potentially effective combinations of socio-legal pathways.

All these leverage points are legal and policy elements but directly relate to the environmental domain and empower that domain directly. This means that while they are embedded in socio-economic frameworks, their primary impact is on environmental sustainability and protection, influencing biodiversity and ecological health directly rather than through food system activities. It aims to inherently change the relation of human to nature, therefore changes both production and consumption systems.

3.1 Environmental due diligence

The due diligence pathway can be seen as one of the mechanisms used to ensure compliance with environmental standards and regulations. Due diligence, as defined in the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights, is a process by which businesses prevent, address, and remedy impacts on human rights and the environment arising from their own operations and business relationships throughout their supply chain. This places it firmly within the sphere of corporate responsibility and behaviour within the food system.

Due diligence involves assessing and mitigating environmental impacts throughout the food production and supply chain processes. The paper explicitly describes Human Rights and Environmental Due Diligence (HREDD) laws and the EU Regulation on Deforestation (EUDR) as supply chain instruments. The EUDR, for example, specifically targets the import and export of certain forest-risk commodities (cattle, cocoa, coffee, palm oil, soy, rubber, and wood) and requires companies to exercise mandatory risk-based due diligence to ensure their production is not linked to deforestation. This indicates that due diligence in this context focuses heavily on the primary production and sourcing stages of the food system, aiming to ensure environmentally sound practices at the origin of food commodities. By imposing obligations on value chain companies, including operators and traders, due diligence mechanisms like the EUDR aim to institutionalize new standards of corporate accountability in the global South, where many food commodities are produced. This highlights the role of due diligence in regulating the flow of goods from production regions to consumer markets within the food system.

The key pathway around environmental due diligence (EDD) from a consumer governance perspective primarily involves the use of supply chain instruments designed to reform corporate practice within consuming jurisdictions. However, the study characterizes these measures as having less transformative potential for achieving biodiversity conservation and equity. Firstly, the study found that due diligence laws are largely based on a reformist approach. They seek only to modify or reform corporate practice to increase sustainability and treat the market economy and growth as common sense. They generally impose no constraints on consumption and fail to tackle the

wider macro-economy and accumulation imperatives. In addition, environmental due diligence laws tend to enforce rigid distinctions between humans and nature. Deforestation Due Diligence, in particular, is mainly anthropocentric, viewing nature (e.g., timber) as a resource to be wisely managed for global value chains, rather than challenging the underlying capitalist relations that necessitate the resource framing. Lastly, the design of due diligence regulations raises concerns regarding equity. Specifically, the EUDR may have potential negative impacts on smallholders, Indigenous Peoples, and local communities (IPLCs) due to supply chain exclusions or inadequate price premiums to cover compliance costs. This could result in IPLCs being pushed onto marginal lands. Generally, laws that sustain Cartesian dichotomies, even when focusing on biodiversity, have historically led to dispossession and violations of rights for Indigenous Peoples and local communities

This implies that while due diligence operates within the food system, its transformative potential for broader sustainability and multi-species justice is limited if it does not address deeper systemic issues. Another provided critique is that instruments like the EUDR, while significant, may have a narrow scope (e.g., focusing only on forests and potentially excluding other critical ecosystems). This suggests that the leverage of due diligence within the food system might be constrained by the specific environmental or human rights issues it targets.

3.2 Rights of nature and legal personhood

The pathway of creating Rights of Nature (RoN) and legal personhood for achieving transformative change for biodiversity and equity is understood not as a conventional consumer governance instrument (like due diligence), but as a more transformative legal and ontological shift that addresses the root causes of socio-ecological damage, which traditional consumer-side regulation fails to resolve.

RoN introduces a paradigm shift in environmental law and governance. It necessitates a move beyond traditional anthropocentric or even biocentric approaches by embedding the rights of nature into legal and policy frameworks. The most transformative potential is achieved when RoN principles embrace "naturehood for people". This involves adopting principles that recognize the entanglement of human-nature relations, non-human agency, and value (ethics of care), making space for plural philosophies. This ontological shift provides a profound challenge to instrumentalist views of nature often perpetuated by consumer-driven economies. This can influence the development of new regulations concerning land use, water management, and biodiversity conservation within agricultural landscapes and beyond. The establishment of guardianship for entities like New Zealand's Whanganui River exemplifies how RoN requires new governance structures that include representation for the rights and well-being of nature.

RoN directly impacts the foundation of food production by granting legal rights to natural entities like rivers, forests, and ecosystems. This could fundamentally alter how food is produced by emphasizing the intrinsic value of nature and its right to exist and regenerate, rather than solely viewing it as a resource for human use. For instance, granting legal personhood to a river could restrict agricultural practices that pollute it or deplete its water resources. Similarly, recognizing the rights of a forest could limit deforestation for agricultural expansion, as highlighted by the EU Regulation on Deforestation (EUDR) aiming to prevent deforestation linked to certain commodities.

The RoN pathway directly addresses the key limitation of consumer governance instruments like Deforestation Due Diligence (DD), which seek only to reform corporate practice and treat the market economy as common sense. RoN gives local communities more power to defend ecosystems. This is important for equity, as it counters the historical exclusion of Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities (IPLCs) from law and policy making and counters the potential dispossession that anthropocentric or biocentric laws can cause. In jurisdictions where RoN is adopted, community guardians or Indigenous representatives are often appointed to represent the rights of the ecosystem (e.g., New Zealand's Whanganui River).

For RoN to be practical and effective against corporate behaviours driven by global consumer demands (which result in environmental crime), the study suggests combining RoN with other legal mechanisms (e.g., environmental courts). This combination represents a practical way to hold violators accountable and deter further destruction linked to accumulation pressures: Environmental Courts and Tribunals (ECTs) ECTs provide a viable pathway for implementing RoN

because they offer expertise, efficiency, and greater accountability for crimes against nature. However, courts cannot yet address transnational environmental crimes or crimes committed by transnational corporations.

However, the paper also highlights important considerations for placing this lever within pathways: Implementing RoN within the food system may lead to conflicts with existing practices and economic interests focused solely on maximizing food production. The paper discusses challenges in enforcing RoN, such as the ability of guardianship bodies to institute legal proceedings and security risks preventing action against violators. The paper suggests that the efficacy of RoN is enhanced when aligned with Indigenous and other relational philosophies that recognize the interconnectedness of humans and nature. Without this broader societal shift, RoN might risk reinforcing human-nature dichotomies. The concept of "naturehood" to humans is introduced as a necessary complement, involving new understandings of the balance between humans and other members of Earth's life systems. Lastly, the paper argues that truly transformative change requires more than just legal recognition of RoN. It necessitates ontological shifts in consciousness and ways of being that recognize the agency and vitality of non-humans. This implies that the lever of RoN needs to be coupled with emancipatory education, social movements, and socio-cultural engagements to foster a deeper understanding and respect for nature within the context of food systems.

3.3 Ecocide as an international crime

A pathway of establishing ecocide as an international crime, represents a mechanism intended to achieve transformative change by holding powerful actors accountable for severe environmental destruction, thereby creating a deterrent effect that impacts corporate behaviour driven by global consumption and accumulation imperatives. This mechanism is categorized as a more radical proposition compared to mainstream consumer governance tools like due diligence.

The goal is to add Ecocide to the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court (ICC), sitting alongside crimes like genocide and war crimes, to make it an arrestable offense. By levying responsibility on natural persons (living human beings) rather than legal fictional entities (like corporations), the pathway aims to end the "cycle of destruction and accrual of silent rights (the right to pollute, the right to destroy). If adopted internationally, the Statute underscores the gravity of the crime and would act as a strong deterrent, reinforcing existing environmental laws and making non-binding agreements (like the Paris Agreement) easier to adhere to. Since everyday activities, including consumption, travel, and work, contribute to ecological harms, this deterrent effect targets the destructive accumulation driven by consumer demand.

Ecocide would directly impact the way food is produced by criminalizing large-scale environmental destruction associated with these activities. This could deter practices leading to: 1) Widespread deforestation for agricultural expansion (relevant to commodities like cattle, soy, palm oil mentioned in the context of the EUDR). Acts considered ecocidal could include the destruction of vast forest areas with *"severe and either widespread or long-term damage to the environment"*. 2) Pollution of water bodies from agricultural runoff, industrial aquaculture, or other food production processes that cause very serious adverse changes, disruption or harm to aquatic ecosystems. The case in Guatemala where a palm oil corporation polluted waterways, despite a ruling against it, highlights the need for stronger enforcement mechanisms that ecocide aims to provide. 3) Destruction of soil health and biodiversity through unsustainable farming practices that lead to "long-term" and "widespread" degradation. 4) Harm to marine ecosystems from destructive fishing practices causing *"grave impacts on human life or natural, cultural or economic resources"*.

This could influence corporate behaviour throughout food value chains by holding individual actors within corporations liable for ecocidal acts. In addition, it could complement existing Human Rights and Environmental Due Diligence (HREDD) laws and regulations like the EUDR by providing a stronger deterrent against the most severe forms of environmental damage. It could also potentially reinforce existing environmental laws and make adherence to non-binding agreements easier by establishing a higher legal standard for environmental protection. Lastly, it could raise public awareness and potentially shift cultural norms around environmental destruction related to food production and consumption. The mock ecocide trial suggests the potential for raising awareness and promoting dialogue.

However, the paper also highlights challenges and nuances that affect the placement and impact. The current proposed definition of ecocide includes a "wantonness" element, which considers whether environmental damage is "*clearly excessive in relation to the social and economic benefits anticipated*". This anthropocentric framing could limit its effectiveness in challenging food production practices deemed economically beneficial, even if environmentally damaging. As seen in the Guatemalan case, legal recognition of environmental crimes is insufficient without effective enforcement mechanisms. The ICC's limited reach and the difficulties in prosecuting complex, transboundary environmental crimes pose challenges for holding actors within global food systems accountable for ecocide.

The ICC currently has jurisdiction over natural persons, not legal entities like corporations. While individuals within corporations could be prosecuted, holding the entire corporate structure accountable for systemic ecocidal practices might be challenging at the international level. Some national laws, like Belgium's, aim to include corporations. The paper suggests that Ecocide is assessed as having less transformative potential unless significant changes are made to its legal definition and implementation. Its potential is enhanced when combined with other transformative instruments.

3.4 Restorative Justice as an enforcement mechanism

The Restorative Justice (RJ) pathway for transformative change for biodiversity and equity, when viewed from a consumer governance perspective, is not a standalone value or supply chain instrument but rather a judicial enforcement mechanism. It is part of a "more transformative" legal pathway that combines the radical philosophical shift of the Rights of Nature (RoN) with practical court processes, intended to deter the destructive accumulation driven by global consumption. Restorative Justice focuses on harm reparation, social restoration, community harmony, and problem-solving. In the context of environmental damage caused by corporations operating to meet global consumption demands, RJ provides a means of addressing the harm caused by these activities and involving affected communities in the resolution. When food production activities (agriculture, fisheries, forestry, etc.) cause environmental damage, such as pollution or habitat destruction, restorative justice offers a mechanism to address these harms. This could involve environmental restoration initiatives, apologies from the responsible parties, and potential compensation for the damage. The paper notes that in Canada and New Zealand, trees and rivers have been acknowledged as victims in restorative justice processes related to environmental crime.

The RJ pathway faces certain limitations: Although Preston (2011) argues for RJ because the biosphere and non-human biota have intrinsic value, his framework is noted to still reinforce human-nature dichotomies. The risk remains that RJ might focus on relationality only where local communities already possess these philosophies, rather than enabling the widespread ontological regeneration needed to challenge colonial modernities globally. Like other judicial mechanisms, RJ and the combined approach can create a deterrent effect and punish wrongdoers, but "it does not dismantle the capitalist system" itself, which is the driving force behind ecologically destructive accumulation. Lastly, for RJ to achieve its full potential, it requires communities to have or be supported to unlearn colonial modernities and co-create new imaginaries of human-nature relations, particularly in societies imbued with solely instrumentalist relations to nature. The paper also cautions against reinforcing human-nature dichotomies and emphasizes the importance of understanding the entangled and often spiritual relationships that Indigenous Peoples have with the land. The mock ecocide trial described in the paper demonstrated the potential of restorative justice hearings to enable dialogue between diverse human and non-human interests affected by environmental harm, aiming for voice, healing, and restoration.

3.4 Environmental courts and tribunals

The pathway of Environmental Courts and Tribunals (ECTs) for transformative change, viewed from a consumer governance side, is primarily as an enforcement and implementation mechanism. ECTs provide a practical judicial forum for enacting the more radical legal concepts (Rights of Nature and Ecocide) that directly challenge the ecologically destructive accumulation driven by global consumption. While ECTs themselves are not supply chain instruments like Due Diligence, their effectiveness in prosecuting environmental harm and enforcing restorative remedies creates a deterrent effect on corporate behaviour associated with global consumer markets.

ECTs could be invoked when environmental damage occurs at any stage of the food value chain. This could include issues like pollution from agricultural runoff, deforestation linked to commodity production, illegal fishing practices, or environmental damage caused by food processing and waste management. The paper explicitly states that ECTs could provide a pathway for implementing Rights of Nature (RoN). If natural entities within the food system (e.g., forests cleared for agriculture, rivers affected by pollution) are granted legal personhood, ECTs would be the forums where their rights could be defended and enforced.

ECTs aim to provide greater accountability for crimes against nature. This could involve prosecuting individuals or corporations responsible for environmental damage within the food system, acting as a deterrent against harmful practices. ECTs can increase opportunities to use alternative dispute resolutions, such as Restorative Justice. The establishment and effective operation of ECTs can signify visible government support for environmental protection and provide a focus for public attention on environmental issues within the food system. They contribute to the broader governance framework by offering a specialized legal avenue for environmental concerns. The paper notes that the expertise, efficiency, and lower costs of some ECTs are positives. This suggests that they can provide a more accessible and effective way to address environmental issues in the food system compared to traditional court systems.

The paper notes challenges associated with ECTs, such as the risk of sidelining environmental cases and issues relating to the definition of what constitutes an environmental issue. Therefore, their effectiveness within a food system and value chain would depend on their specific design, resources, and integration with other regulatory and justice mechanisms.

4. Consumer behaviour and retail environments

Work package 2.3 analysed of product labels, corporate brands, marketing strategies, and benchmarks to assess potential influence on consumer behaviour, including their food purchase decisions, and biodiversity/equity outcomes inform development of transformative change pathways. Here the term consumer is used to refer to individual citizens, as end consumers of agri-commodities.

The report by Ingenbleek et al (2025) adopts a consumer-centered perspective to map the policy and behavioural instruments that can help transform telecoupled value chains toward greater equity, biodiversity, and sustainability. The aim of this study was to describe the measures currently implemented or debated, but also to identify emerging pathways for change shaped by consumers' own perceptions and preferences. To do so, the authors developed a comprehensive set of eleven instruments spanning diverse approaches to influencing consumer behaviour and market dynamics. Rather than privileging options that dominate public or academic discussions, we deliberately considered the full range of possible interventions and assessed their perceived potential among consumers. The mapping is informed by survey data from 1,515 consumers in Sweden, the Netherlands, and Italy. In all three countries, the results point to a strong appetite for transformation: when respondents were presented with multiple policy options, "no change" was consistently among the least preferred. A central motivation for this work is to move beyond the prevailing emphasis on sustainability labels. While labels are widely viewed as a remedy for information asymmetries in global value chains, their effectiveness relies on assumptions of rational, informed, and highly motivated consumers—assumptions that do not always hold in practice. Our findings confirm that although labels are familiar tools, consumers' awareness and consistent use of them remain limited. By broadening the lens from information provision to the wider context in which choices are made, this chapter explores how different instruments inform, aid, steer, or restrict consumer decisions. Notably, consumers in all three countries evaluated these instruments in strikingly similar ways, revealing shared priorities and expectations regarding fairness and responsibility in sustainable consumption.

The consumer surveys revealed that the retail environment is highly influential for consumer behaviour and has most potential for change. Government interventions, like awareness campaigns, were less influential on consumer behaviours/perceptions. We further examined aspects like ethical consumer behaviour, self-efficacy, perceived consumer effectiveness, and

autonomy. Consumers are simultaneously satisfied and frustrated with their autonomy. This finding suggests that they feel comfortable with the current supermarket-dominated environment, but at the same time they perceive it as a dead-end road to solving sustainability problems through consumer decisions. We included an option of no change, where things stay as they currently are. Interestingly, and in line with the result that consumers feel frustration about their autonomy, this option of no change ranks lower than all different forms of change offered.

Consumers prioritised: (1) price interventions: decreasing prices of sustainable products while increasing prices of unsustainable products, (2) strengthening sustainability labels and providing more reminders about them in store, (3) providing more sustainability rankings in which products, brands and companies are ranked in terms of sustainability, (4) rewarding sustainable purchases with loyalty points for nice extra's, (5) more education campaigns for sustainable decision-making, (6) positioning stores more clearly at one sustainability level so that the trade-off between sustainability and price rests more on the store choice rather than on all individual product choices, (7) stimulating unintended purchases "tricking" consumers in buying sustainable products, (8) offer tools that help consumers to pre-select their products so that they get less distracted by the store environment, (9) banning unsustainable products by law, and (10) licensing the availability of unsustainable products so that they are only available for groups that may really need them (like for food banks) (for more information please see D2.3).

These findings suggest the following pathways:

4.1 Retail environment pathway

Consumer surveys shows that the retail environment is influential, with price actions for sustainable products, pointers and markers to these products, and nudges, like placing them on eye level in the supermarket shelves, coming out as the most used instruments (with the results being fairly consistent across the three countries). Transforming the retail environment (physical and online) would make sustainable options more visible, affordable, and convenient, shifting everyday purchasing patterns without relying on constant consumer vigilance. When millions of small choices begin to favour products with lower ecological footprints or fairer social practices, retailers are incentivized to source differently, and producers are pushed toward more biodiversity-friendly farming and more equitable labour conditions. Over time, these shifts in demand can reshape entire value chains, reducing pressures on biodiversity-rich regions and improving the livelihoods of producers who adopt sustainable practices. At the same time, redesigning store environments reduces structural barriers that currently place too much responsibility on consumers. Pricing interventions, clearer information on shelves, and strategic product placement shift the burden from individuals to the actors who shape the architecture of choice, retailers, brands, and policymakers. This makes access to sustainable options more equitable, particularly for lower-income consumers who are often priced out of environmentally responsible choices. It also redistributes responsibility more fairly across the chain, recognizing that transformative change requires systemic support rather than isolated consumer effort.

4.2 Product information and labelling pathway

The results clearly indicate that consumers value access to clear and reliable information that helps reduce the complexity of making sustainable choices, without limiting their freedom to choose. Rather than placing the burden solely on individuals, consumers express a strong desire for structural changes within their shopping environment that make sustainable options more accessible and attractive. They advocate for pricing strategies that reward sustainable purchases, such as offering lower prices for environmentally friendly products, funded by higher prices for unsustainable alternatives. Additionally, they support loyalty incentives that favour sustainable brands and products, such as exclusive benefits or rewards, rather than the current practice of promoting unsustainable items through discounts and special offers.

Consumers call for improved information and communication around sustainability. This includes strengthening the credibility and visibility of sustainability labels, introducing clear product rankings, and launching educational campaigns to raise awareness and understanding. These measures can help shift the reward mechanisms within supply chains, particularly in sectors like cocoa and coffee, towards outcomes that support biodiversity and social equity, moving beyond price reductions as the primary incentive. Importantly, this transition does not diminish the role of food retailers. Instead, it highlights the need for more active government involvement to guide

competition among retailers in a way that promotes sustainability while keeping the consumer experience straightforward and empowering. In essence, consumers are calling for a shopping environment that enables and encourages sustainable choices; one that aligns economic incentives with environmental and social responsibility.

4.3 Pricing pathway

Overall, this study shows that consumers see price-based measures, especially narrowing the price gap between sustainable and unsustainable products, as the most effective way to support sustainable choices, even while acknowledging that such interventions may limit their freedom. Loyalty programs that reward sustainable purchases also rank surprisingly high, despite receiving little attention in current debates. Consumers value sustainability rankings as well, but prefer them integrated directly into the store rather than delivered through apps or websites, which they rarely use. Overall, the findings highlight a core insight: the shopping environment itself makes sustainable choices unnecessarily difficult. Consumers trust and rely on in-store cues; discounts, placement, clear visuals; far more than external tools. This points to a clear pathway for change: redesigning the store environment to make sustainable options more visible, accessible, and intuitive, while recognizing that such shifts may face resistance from retailers protective of their control over the retail space.

4.4 Legal frameworks pathway

Another pathway is to examine legal frameworks to enable pricing and in-store interventions that promote consumption of biodiverse and equitably produced and traded products. Legal barriers and opportunities for potential interventions in the price system and store environment could create pressure to create the supportive shopping environment that consumers are asking for. Changing the price system is complex system change, as it does not just involve the price levels used in the stores for the prices paid by the consumer, but also the incentives that such prices provide for all the suppliers in the value chains leading to these stores. It is in the chain, in particular at the basis of the chain, where the most important impact can be made for sustainability. Although consumers don't rate these as so likeable, legal bans due to them reduced choice of freedom. We write "perceived" because only in the cases of licensing and legal bans, choice of freedom is reduced.

4.5 Public debates pathway

A practical pathway for advancing more sustainable food systems, beginning with shifting the focus from consumer blame to the role of retailers in shaping choice. One way recommended is to launch public debates on supermarkets' responsibilities, creating dialogue platforms to explore new business models.

4.6 Consumer-product-retailer feedback loops

Another pathway involves strengthening feedback loops so that consumers can see the real sustainability impacts of their choices, an idea that respondents in Italy and Sweden found particularly appealing. The study also notes limitations, such as its focus on supermarket shoppers and the influence of familiarity on consumer preferences, and calls for future research that includes online and alternative food environments. Overall, the findings show that consumers are ready for change and favour interventions that make sustainable options more visible, accessible, and rewarding, suggesting that meaningful transformation depends on redesigning the environments in which choices are made.

Strengthening feedback loops adds another important dimension by making the real impacts of food production visible to consumers. When information about biodiversity loss, ecosystem health, or social inequities is fed back into the consumer environment, the system becomes more adaptive: consumers can see the consequences of their choices, producers gain incentives to improve practices, and retailers respond to evolving expectations. Such feedback could help correct the current imbalance, where signals primarily flow from consumers to producers through price, often encouraging efficiencies that harm biodiversity and equity.

5. Collective action

Deliverable 2.4 on **Social movements and collective action in processes of sustainability transformations**, maps, characterises and assesses consumer country transformative governance innovations for biodiversity and equity. The Social Learning implemented in Work Package 5 has generated methodological innovations for exploring futures that unsettle fixed notions of modernity and human–nature relations, extending from production and conservation landscapes to sites of consumption and governance. New approaches with producers in high biodiversity, forested production landscapes and with consumers in other activities in Work Package 2 reveal the hidden relational and political dimensions of telecoupled value chains. Findings show how “imaginaries”—particularly by smallholders and stakeholders in export crop production systems—remain constrained, though not fully determined, by colonial modernity, with escape paths often obstructed by violence, corruption, elitism, and militarisation. While structural barriers to transformative change persist, collaborations with artists and environmental humanities have opened creative possibilities for recognising more-than-human agencies and cultivating care-oriented relations. This work informs an emerging concept of “societal learning” that embraces plural human–nature relations and fosters critical consciousness of colonial modernity in futures exploration.

Further, five studies provide diverse examples of different aspects of collective action and social movements and their governance in agroecology, conservation, and agri-food transitions. The first study evaluates the management plan of the Sierra Nevada de Santa Marta and Tayrona National Parks, finding strong intercultural and rights-based elements but lacking structural transformation, broad participation, and clear implementation pathways. The second study explores ontological pluralism among non-indigenous agroecological farmers in the Aburrá Valley, highlighting how farmers navigate heterogeneous knowledge systems and power dynamics in sustainable agriculture. The third study analyzes women’s empowerment in a community-based conservation project, identifying economic, social, psychological, and political empowerment—plus a new category, ecological empowerment—while revealing how intersectional identities shape outcomes. The fourth study investigates coffee growers’ perceptions of deforestation and the EU Deforestation Regulation (EUDR), uncovering major conceptual gaps, structural barriers, and economic tensions, while noting that the Jaguar Friendly label promotes conservation ethics but remains economically fragile. The fifth study assesses permaculture initiatives (PIs) in Southwestern Catalunya and concludes that while PIs advance environmental sustainability and challenge dominant agri-food systems, limitations in scaling and insufficient socio-economic strategies prevent them from functioning as pathways for systemic transition.

Across the five studies, a coherent theme emerges: transformative environmental governance and sustainable transitions require deep structural change, broader equity, and recognition of diverse forms of knowledge and empowerment. They show how indigenous and local knowledge systems are essential but often only partially integrated into interventions and efforts for change. Power dynamics—gendered, cultural, economic—shape who benefits from conservation and sustainability interventions. The studies all emphasise that successful transitions require systemic approaches, inclusive participation, and pathways that go beyond localized or symbolic efforts.

6. Learning from trade legal and consumer insights for pathways

This section identifies the different recommendations from a consumption governance point of view that emerge from the work package 2 deliverables. The focus lies on outlining the overarching directions for change rather than providing an exhaustive exploration or all possible combinations of measures. Three distinct but interrelated pathways can be discerned.

The following recommendations are summarised from each deliverable:

Deliverable and domain	Recommendation
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2.2 International Trade	Strengthening sustainability criteria in trade agreements and environmental policy and land governance reforms in producing countries, supported by consuming countries, is more effective than relying on voluntary standards. Producer country-led certification systems are valuable when supported by consumer countries, as short-term reform-oriented measures.
2.2 International Trade	Deep leverage points to transform global economies are needed, not only value chain measures. This includes cancelling debt for former colonized nations to enable economic restructuring, steps to decolonize knowledge systems and support for fair, community-based solidarity economies .
2.2 International Trade	Improve governance through increased civil society participation , plus support for Indigenous Peoples' and local community relational land care .
2.2 International Trade	Implement comprehensive footprint accounting in trade measures and introduce ecological premiums on resource-intensive imports to ensure fair compensation and reward sustainable production for producers in resource-rich countries.
2.2 International Trade	reductions in agri commodity material consumption by wealthier nations based on robust consumption-based governance .
2.2 Legal Actions	Adopt legal frameworks that grant " naturehood " to humans to foster a sense of responsibility and connection towards the environment.
2.2 Legal Actions	Clarify the definition of ecocide removing the "wantonness" element to overcome human-nature
2.2 Legal Actions	Combine Rights of Nature, Ecocide, and Restorative Justice with environmental courts to provide a practical way to re-balance concerns for human and ecological needs.
2.2 Legal Actions	Grant ' naturehood ' rather than legal personhood to humans, recognising the broader assemblages that co-create life.
2.2 Legal Actions	Invest in educational initiatives, artistic engagements, transdisciplinary research , and support for social movements to change human-nature relations to ones based on care and reciprocity, give voice to non-humans in governance and generate support for public and governmental action.
2.4 Consumer	Modifying the retail environment , initiating public debates on the role of retailers and statutory means of enabling responsible consumption, organizing roundtable discussions with retailers and value chain actors, and exploring legislative measures to support such transformations.
2.4 Consumer	Improved information and feedback mechanisms , where sustainability outcomes are made visible to consumers, could help make food systems more adaptive and responsive.

An examination of the deliverables, from legal actions and international trade agreements to consumer market analyses, reveals areas of convergence, divergence, and notable blind spots. Such differences often arise from the distinct disciplinary foundations and epistemological assumptions that shape each perspective, as well as from differing conceptions of transformative change. The observed diversity in responses underscores how disciplinary positioning fundamentally influences both the framing of problems and the formulation of corresponding solutions, thereby raising questions about the extent to which a common language or conceptual framework can be harmonized across these domains.

6.1 Consumption-Driven Leverage Points

An output of Work package 2.5 is a scientific article by Marina Benitez-Kanter, Caspar Krampe, Verina Jane Ingram, Paul Ingenbleek, Georg Winkel and Marko Lovric on the consumption-driven leverage points which could foster a transformative change of telecoupled value chains towards biodiversity and equity (Benitez-Kanter et al 2025).

The article places biodiversity conservation and social equity as core market driving values is crucial for enabling a transformative change of telecoupled value chains. While various disciplines have proposed interventions and strategies to foster the adoption of these values, there is an increasing need to integrate knowledge across disciplines. To address this gap, an integrative literature review was conducted, identifying the leverage points for fostering transformative change towards biodiversity and equity. We reviewed 214 papers of the research domains of (i) transformative change, (ii) food systems, (iii) governance, and (iv) marketing. We identified 415 leverage points to promote biodiversity and equity within value chains, where laws and regulations, stakeholder collaboration, and the inclusion of diverse perspectives in decision-making processes were the most common across disciplines.

To address the complexity of the interaction across stakeholders and institutions that take place in telecoupled value chains, we argue that transformative change could only be achieved by implementing multiple leverage points, regardless of its classification as deep or shallow. Moreover, for fostering transformative change, these leverage points should be addressed by diverse stakeholders of multiple governance levels simultaneously. The article aims to guide policymakers and value chain actors in identifying the most effective leverage points for driving transformative change towards biodiversity and equity, ensuring an effective governance of telecoupled value chains, where the diverse needs of multiple stakeholders are considered. Besides laws and regulations identified as the most prominent leverage point to secure an effective transformative change of telecoupled food systems identified from different disciplinary perspectives, other leverage points such as technological innovation can be used. Technological innovation could help to secure an effective social inclusion and coordination across stakeholders, as it could provide transparency, accountability and trust in the transactions of money, goods and information across distant places.

6.2 An integrative conceptual framework for transformative change of food telecoupled value chains from the consumption-side perspective

An output of Work package 2.5 is a scientific article by Marina Benitez-Kanter, Caspar Krampe, Verina Ingram, Paul Ingenbleek and Georg Winkel providing an integrative conceptual framework for transformative change of food telecoupled value chains from the consumption-side perspective (Benitez-Kanter et al., *in submission* 2025).

The article argues that transforming food systems is essential to promote biodiversity conservation and social equity. Although various disciplines have proposed diverse interventions, strategies, and actions to place these goals at the center of telecoupled value chains, achieving biodiversity conservation and social equity requires integrating knowledge across disciplines. In this integration, incorporating a consumption-side perspective of the leverage points and transformative change pathways towards sustainability is crucial, as consumption has been identified as one of the main drivers of exploitative telecoupled food systems that produce severe negative impacts on both biodiversity and equity.

To address this gap, this paper presents an integrative conceptual framework that brings together the determinants of transformative change in telecoupled value chains from the consumption-side perspective. The framework – illustrated in figure 1 - synthesizes insights from the literature on transformative change, food systems, governance, and marketing, and enables a comparative analysis of how these disciplines conceptualize change(s) and transformation (s). The figure illustrates a telecoupled value chain as an interconnected food system from producers to consumers, highlighting various stakeholders and actions influencing biodiversity and equity outcomes at multiple governance levels. These stakeholders at multiple governance levels: International Organizations, the public sector, the private sector, societal stakeholders such as NGO and social movements, consumers and producers. These stakeholders can enact different leverage points across telecoupled value chains, both shallow & deep.

The authors suggest four key elements for enabling transformative change of telecoupled value chains: (i) applying systems thinking; (ii) utilizing both shallow and deep leverage points concurrently; (iii) confronting addressing power asymmetries by decentralizing governance, shifting power relations, and embracing plural perspectives; and (iv) promoting stakeholder collaboration and coordination across multiple governance levels. This integrative conceptual framework aims to serve as a starting point for empirical research analyzing leverage points and transformative pathways toward biodiversity conservation and social equity in telecoupled value chains such as coffee and cocoa, particularly from a consumption-side perspective. Moreover, it

offers a practical tool for policymakers, stakeholders, and institutions to identify the most effective leverage points for fostering such change. In doing so, the framework helps ensure that the diverse needs and values of stakeholders across multiple governance levels are recognized and addressed.

Figure 1 Integrative Framework to Transform Telecoupled Value Chains to Foster Biodiversity and Equity

Source: Authors elaboration based on (Gereffi et al., 2005; Ericksen, 2008; Ostrom, 2009; Ingram, 2011; Zurek et al., 2021; and Hermans et al., 2023). The figure illustrates a telecoupled value chain as an interconnected food system from producers to consumers, highlighting various stakeholders and actions influencing biodiversity and equity outcomes at multiple governance levels. These stakeholders at multiple governance levels are represented with icons: 🌐 International Organizations, 🏛️ the public sector, 🏢 the private sector, 🧑 the societal stakeholders such as NGO and social movements, 🧑 consumers and 🧑 producers. These stakeholders can enact different leverage points across telecoupled value chains, both shallow (Parameters-blue, feedback-green) & deep (Intent-pink, Design-orange).

6.3 Points of convergence

The work on trade agreements demonstrates that **sustainability standards** have had a positive effects to ensure that commodities are cultivated, sourced, and processed through a predefined set of (internationally used yet co-existing with national regulations) sustainability threshold indicators, covering environmental and social dimensions, for example for cocoa on environmental sustainability indicators. The impact on poverty and income appeared generally positive. Similarly, for coffee, certification tended to have positive effects on environmental sustainability indicators,

while its impact on poverty and income was more mixed, ranging from positive to neutral. Research on consumer markets highlighted consumers' desire for greater visibility of sustainability standards, labels, ranking products on the basis of their sustainability levels, and product information. Enhanced labelling would enable consumers to make more informed choices without restricting their options. These findings imply that the effectiveness of sustainability initiatives depends not only on broader market mechanisms and stakeholder engagement for transparency and information.

The studies show that **legal initiatives** can reinforce the conventional pathway by raising accountability standards. They create stronger incentives for companies to pursue certification, increase NGOs' capacity to hold firms responsible for negative social and ecological impacts, and amplify the effects of naming and shaming strategies. In doing so, legal measures function less as an isolated solution and more as a pressure mechanism that enhances the credibility and effectiveness. As such, legal measures can also support the identified need of changing retail environment, as identified in the consumer market research. This research showcased that there is an important role for food retailers, but motivating these stakeholders adapt the retail environment may require greater intervention of government policy or other incentives to steer competition between retailers in a direction that promotes sustainability.

Based on the consumer market study, it was shown how consumers strongly value their freedom of choice and generally oppose the outright banning of products, even when those products are considered unsustainable or unhealthy. However, they are receptive to **price-based interventions** that guide purchasing behaviour without restricting options. Specifically, they support mechanisms that make sustainable or healthier products more affordable, while increasing the cost of less sustainable or harmful alternatives. This approach aligns with broader discussions in international trade and public health policy, such as proposals for taxes on products high in fat or sugar, which aim to internalize the societal costs of consumption. By adjusting price signals rather than limiting availability, such strategies preserve consumer autonomy while promoting more responsible choices, suggesting a pathway for policy that balances market freedom with sustainability and health objectives.

6.4 Points of divergence

Some contrasts can also be observed across the studies. The work on international trade agreement emphasizes the **high level of consumption of tropical forest-risk commodities**, such as palm oil, cocoa, and coffee, by high-income countries (HICs), noting that per capita consumption in low-income regions has risen significantly. The benefits associated with consumption and telecoupled to high environmental and social footprints in the production countries. One pathway to reduce overall consumption as a way to mitigate environmental impacts. However, this view contrasts with insights from consumer market research, which emphasize that consumers value their **freedom of choice** and generally resist restrictive measures such as product bans. Consumers tend to favour approaches that preserve choice while promoting sustainability, such as purchasing certified products that ensure responsible sourcing. This contrasts with approaches by regulation, trade agreements and certification which seek to minimise or mitigate footprints and impacts, rather than decrease the quantity of commodities produced and change or decrease trade to HICs. This highlights a tension between systemic calls for consumption reduction and consumer-driven strategies that focus on informed, ethical purchasing. Bridging this gap may require policy instruments, such as differentiated pricing, taxes on unsustainable goods (e.g., those high in fat or sugar), or trade regulations, that guide behaviour without undermining consumer autonomy.

All the studies suggest that while conventional measures remain central, they will need to be **intensified and adapted to specific consumer preferences and contexts** in different countries and regions in order to address ongoing shortcomings. Especially, the work on legal actions and international trade, argue that fundamental pathways for achieving transformative change for biodiversity and equity should focus on **deep systemic and ontological shifts**. These transformations necessitate challenging the foundations of modern society, including worldviews, beliefs and values, specifically by overcoming rigid Cartesian dichotomies between humans and nature and confronting capitalist accumulation and colonial modernity imperatives. To support biodiversity, pathways include shifts towards plural and relational ontologies, recognizing non-human agency and value. For equity, this involves recognizing that socio-ecological degradation stems from power inequalities and concentrations of wealth.

In terms of concrete legal and policy pathways, transformative approaches involve combining several **emerging legal levers with radical economic reforms**. Legal pathways with potential include implementing Rights of Nature (RoN), granting 'naturehood' to persons to recognize human-nature entanglement, and combining this with Restorative Justice in specialized environmental courts to ensure harm reparation, social restoration, and community harmony. These pathways could ensure that producers, including Indigenous communities, and consumers have a central role as decision-makers and can defend ecosystems effectively. Furthermore, the introduction of the international crime of Ecocide (especially if defined to fully address capitalist pressures and remove anthropocentric limitations) has the potential to challenge capitalist relations by prosecuting powerful actors responsible for severe environmental destruction. According to the study on legal actions, macro-economic prescriptions focused on equity are needed, such as debt cancellation for poorer nations that were colonized, taxing agro-commodity companies to internalize their social and environmental impacts, and applying progressive taxation to high-net-worth individuals who disproportionately contribute to environmental impacts.

To this end, the studies display different views on transformative change (incremental versus radical), and the role of collective and community/institutions versus individual consumers, also preferences for specific interventions and pathways. On one hand, some studies advocate for shallow and incremental changes, emphasizing gradual improvements through consumer behaviour, market adjustments, and voluntary actions. On the other hand, others argue for deep and radical transformation, which involves systemic shifts in institutions, policies, and societal norms. Therefore the range of approaches is presented. This divergence also reflects differing views on agency: while some place responsibility on individual consumers to drive change through informed choices, others stress the importance of collective action and the role of communities and institutions, such as governments, retailers, and civil society, in creating enabling environments and structural incentives. Together, these perspectives suggest that meaningful progress likely requires a combination of both approaches and stakeholders: empowering individuals while also reshaping the systems in which they operate.

6.5 Uncertainties and implications for further research

Important uncertainties remain, particularly regarding how global-level changes, such as shifts in international trade dynamics, translate into national production and consumption contexts and specific retail environments. For instance, while trade agreements may aim to reduce the consumption of forest-risk commodities and address the footprint and impacts of commodity production, it is not yet clear how international and macro-level strategies influence consumer behaviour at the point of sale or within local retail systems. As a potential point of convergence, the authors of the consumer market research note based on consumer surveys that pricing changes will influence value chains and consumer behaviour, as retail prices can create incentives throughout a chain. Similarly, questions persist about how legal and policy instruments can effectively support the leverage points identified in consumer market research, such as price interventions, consumer choice and sustainability labelling. Addressing these gaps requires a deeper understanding of the roles and perspectives of additional stakeholders and how they relate, including the retailers who shape the consumer experience, intermediaries within supply chains who influence sourcing and pricing, and governments that design and implement supportive policies, regulations, and subsidies. Bridging these layers of influence and interest is essential for aligning systemic change in production systems in low-income, high biodiversity locations with consumer-driven sustainability efforts in the EU and UK.

7. Conclusions

The concluding remarks, drawn from an examination of deliverables spanning legal actions, international trade, and consumer market analysis, identify that achieving transformative change for biodiversity and equity necessitates addressing both immediate, incremental adjustments and fundamental, deep systemic shifts. The differences observed across these domains often stem from distinct disciplinary foundations and differing conceptions of transformative change. However, several points of convergence offer clear pathways forward, suggesting that meaningful progress requires harmonizing a range of approaches and engaging multiple stakeholders.

Several critical pathways emerge where international trade standards, consumer preferences, and legal mechanisms align to reinforce sustainability efforts:

1. Leveraging sustainability standards and visibility through transparency: There is a convergence between the effectiveness of sustainability standards in international trade and consumer demand for transparency in the market. Studies on international trade demonstrated that sustainability standards have had positive effects on environmental indicators for commodities like cocoa and coffee, with generally positive or mixed-to-neutral impacts on poverty and income. This success aligns with consumer market research, which highlights consumers' desire for improved feedback mechanisms where sustainability outcomes are made visible.
2. Utilizing legal initiatives to drive accountability and retail transformation: Legal measures function as a pressure mechanism that can reinforce conventional pathways by raising accountability standards. The studies indicate that legal initiatives create stronger incentives for companies to pursue certification, increase the capacity of Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) to hold firms responsible for negative social and ecological impacts. Crucially, this convergence pathway allows legal measures to support the recognized need for changing the retail environment, as identified in consumer market research. While food retailers have an important role, motivating them to adapt the store environment may require greater intervention through government policy or other incentives to steer competition toward promoting sustainability.
3. Implementing price-based Interventions over restrictive bans: A third point of convergence focuses on using price signals to guide purchasing behaviour. Consumers strongly value their freedom of choice and generally oppose the outright banning of products, even those deemed unsustainable or unhealthy. However, consumers are receptive to interventions that make sustainable or healthier products more affordable while simultaneously increasing the cost of less sustainable or harmful alternatives. This approach aligns with broader policy discussions in international trade and public health, such as proposals for taxes on goods high in fat or sugar, which aim to internalize the societal costs of consumption. By adjusting price signals, these strategies preserve consumer autonomy while promoting more responsible choices, and they are noted as a potential point of convergence that will influence value chains, as retail prices should create the appropriate incentives throughout the chain.
4. While conventional measures must be intensified, the deliverables on legal actions and international trade emphasize that fundamental pathways for achieving transformative change for biodiversity and equity require focusing on deep systemic and ontological shifts. These transformations necessitate challenging the foundations of modern society, including rigid Cartesian dichotomies between humans and nature, and confronting capitalist accumulation and colonial modernity imperatives. For biodiversity, transformative change requires a shift toward plural and relational ontologies, which recognize non-human agency and value. For equity, Systemic transformation requires recognizing that socio-ecological degradation often stems from power inequalities and concentrations of wealth.

Therefore, meaningful progress requires a dual strategy: empowering individuals and adjusting market incentives (incremental change) while simultaneously reshaping the fundamental systems (systemic shifts) through radical transformations in institutions, policies, and societal norms. Bridging the layers of influence, from international trade dynamics to local retail environments and legal frameworks, is essential for aligning transformative change from a consumer governance point of view.

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